

1 **Food Phytochemicals Act as *Quorum Sensing* Inhibitors Reducing Production**
2 **and/or Degrading Autoinducers of *Yersinia enterocolitica* and *Erwinia carotovora***

3
4 Pilar Truchado, Francisco A. Tomás-Barberán, Mar Larrosa and Ana Allende*

5
6 ¹Research Group on Quality, Safety and Bioactivity of Plant Foods, CEBAS-CSIC, P.O.
7 Box 164, Espinardo, Murcia, 30100, Spain.

8
9 **Running Head:** Selected Fruit and Vegetable Bioactive Compounds as *QS* Inhibitors

10
11 **Keywords:** Cell-to-cell communication; *N*-acyl-homoserine lactones; Vegetable
12 extracts; Quorum Quenching; LC-MS/MS spectrometry; microbial growth.

13

* To whom correspondence should be addressed. Telephone: +34-968-396-377; Fax:
+34-968-396-213; E-mail: aallende@cebas.csic.es

1 **Abstract**

2 Bacteria use *Quorum Sensing* (QS) systems to monitor their population density and to
3 control a variety of physiological processes. In this study, the capacity of eleven
4 phenolic compounds to inhibit QS signals in a biosensor strain (*Chromobacterium*
5 *violaceum*) and two pathogenic bacteria (*Yersinia enterocolitica* and *Erwinia*
6 *carotovora*) was evaluated. All the tested compounds inhibited QS regulated
7 phenotypes in the biosensor strain. The identification and quantification of *N*-acyl-
8 homoserine lactones (AHLs) by LC-MS/MS spectrometry showed that cinnamaldehyde,
9 ellagic acid, pomegranate extract, resveratrol and rutin, at concentrations below their
10 minimum inhibitory concentration, were able to reduce concentration of AHLs of both
11 *Y. enterocolitica* and *E. carotovora*.

12

13

1 **1. Introduction**

2 *Quorum Sensing* (QS) is a communication system that allows bacteria to monitor
3 their population density through the production and sensing of small signal molecules
4 called autoinducers (Bassler, 1999; Brackman, Hillaert, Van-Calebergh, Nelis, &
5 Coenye, 2009). Gram positive quorum sensing bacteria use peptides as autoinducers
6 whereas in Gram negative bacteria the most commons autoinducers are N-acyl-
7 homoserine lactones (AHLs). Bacteria employ QS systems to control a variety of
8 physiological processes including secretion of virulence factors and biofilm formation
9 (Rudrappa & Bais, 2008; Ni, Li, Wang, & Wang, 2009). The discovery of QS might
10 have opened a new line of action against microorganisms. The control of bacterial
11 virulence and biofilm formation could have many applications like avoiding biofouling
12 in engineering systems (Xiong & Liu, 2010), reducing bacterial virulence against plants
13 (Dong, Xu, Li, & Zhang, 2000) and as alternative or co-adjuvant therapy in bacteria
14 infections (Lynch & Wiener-Kronish, 2008).

15 The ideal QS inhibitors have been defined as chemically stable and highly
16 effective low-molecular-mass molecules, which exhibit a high degree of specificity for
17 the QS regulator without toxic side effects (Rasmussen & Givskov, 2006). In the last
18 years, some studies have identified QSI in a variety of medicinal and dietary plants
19 (Teplitski, Robinson, & Bauer, 2000; Gao, Teplitski, Robinson, & Bauer, 2003; Vattem,
20 Mihalik, Crixell, & McLean, 2007; Adonizio, Downum, Bennet & Mathee, 2006;
21 Brahma, Singh, Singh, Prakash, Sarma et al. 2009) and phytochemicals have been
22 presented as new antipathogenic agents to control microbial infections via the inhibition
23 of *Quorum Sensing* (Al-Hussaini & Mahasneh, 2009; Brackman et al., 2009; Huber,
24 Eberl, Feucht, & Polster, 2003; Vikram, Jesudhasan, Jayaprakasha, Pillai, & Patil,
25 2010). Thus, the detection of antipathogenic phytochemicals that inhibit the QS

1 regulation of bacterial colonization and virulence factor production might represent a
2 very promising alternative as anti-infective agents (Coates, Hu, Bax, & Page, 2002;
3 Martin, Hoven, & Cook, 2008). Biosensor strains are being commonly used as inhibitor
4 detection systems to evaluate the QS inhibitory effect of phytochemical compounds
5 (Adonizio et al., 2006; Choo, Rukayadi, & Hwang, 2006; Bodini, Manfredini, Epp,
6 Valentini, & Santori, 2009; Brahma et al., 2009; Truchado, López-Gálvez, Gil, Tomás-
7 Barberán, & Allende 2009a). However, although these methods of detection are very
8 useful for screening, the determination of AHLs by liquid chromatography (LC)
9 coupled to mass spectrometry (MS-MS) is a more sensitive and specific method that
10 allows the detection and quantification of specific AHLs (Fekete, Frommberger,
11 Rothballer, Li, Englmann et al., 2007; Fletcher, Diggle, Cámara, & Williams, 2007).

12 Ten compounds found in fruits, herbs and spices were selected: Ellagic, gallic,
13 chlorogenic, vanillic acids and rutin, as compounds found in berries; resveratrol
14 (grapes); kinurenic acid (honey); daidzein (soy); dimethyl-esculetin (artemisia) and
15 pomegranate extract (PE) and cinnamaldehyde was selected as a positive control for QS
16 inhibition (Brackman et al., 2008). In the present study, we evaluated the impact of the
17 selected compounds on the microbial growth, reduction of AHL production by AHL
18 biosensor strain (*Chromobacterium violaceum*) and LC-MS/MS spectrometry (detection
19 of C6 and 3-oxoC6 AHLs) in two bacteria strains: *Erwinia carotovora*, a phytopathogen
20 bacteria that produces plant tissue degrading enzymes by means of QS mechanism (Cui
21 & Harling, 2005), and *Yersinia enterocolitica*, a mammalian enteropathogen, that
22 colonizes the small intestine causing adenitis, septicaemia and gastrointestinal
23 syndromes. The quorum sensing in *Y. enterocolitica* has been reported to play a role in
24 the regulation of motility (Atkinson, Chang, Sockett, Cámara & Williams, 2006).

25

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Strains and culture conditions

Yersinia enterocolitica (CECT 4315), *Erwinia carotovora* (CECT 225) and *Chromobacterium violaceum* (CECT 494) were obtained from the Spanish Type Culture Collection (Valencia, Spain). Stocks of the strains were stored at -80 °C in Luria-Bertani broth (LB broth acc. to MILLER) (Scharlau Chemie, S.A. Barcelona, Spain) with 30% glycerol. When required, strains were routinely grown aerobically with shaking in LB broth for *Y. enterocolitica* and *C. violaceum*, and Potato Dextrose Broth (PDB broth acc. to MILLER) (Scharlau Chemie, S.A. Barcelona, Spain) for *E. carotovora*. All strains were incubated at 30 °C for 24 h. The pH of the culture media was 7.1.

2.2. Quorum Sensing Inhibitors and Acyl-Homoserine Lactones

Table 1 shows the bioactive compounds selected to be tested as QS inhibitors (QSI). Resveratrol, ellagic acid, gallic acid, chlorogenic acid, kinurenic acid and rutin were obtained from Sigma Aldrich (Sigma Chemical, St. Louis, MO). Cinamaldehyde acid (positive control), daidzein, dimethyl-esculetin, were purchased from Extrasynthèse (Genay, France) and vanillic acid from Merck (Darmstadt, Germany). The pomegranate extract (PE, 85% punicalagin, 7% free ellagic acid) “Nutragranate” was obtained from Nutracitrus S.L. (Elche, Spain). Formic acid, ethyl acetate, acetonitrile, methanol (MeOH) and dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO) were obtained from Merck (Darmstadt, Germany). All chemicals were of analytical grade and Milli-Q water was used throughout. Phenolic compounds and PE were initially dissolved in DMSO and filtered through a sterile Millex-GP 0.22 µm filter (Millipore Corp., USA). The

1 selected compounds were added to the culture medium to obtain different
2 concentrations (50, 100 and 200 µg/mL). However, due to its insoluble nature, ellagic
3 acid was tested in lower concentrations (4, 8 and 17 µg/mL). The maximum
4 concentration of DMSO in the assays was 0.1%, which had no effect on bacterial
5 growth. The stock solutions of each compound were stored at -20 °C. The AHL
6 standards used in this study, 3-oxo-C6HSL and C6HSL, were supplied from Sigma (St.
7 Louis, MO).

8

9 2.3. *Quorum Sensing Inhibition Assays*

10 Screening of the QS inhibitory activity of selected phenolic compounds and PE
11 was carried out based on their ability to inhibit the production of purple pigment
12 violacein in *C. violaceum* as previously described (Truchado et al., 2009a). QS in this
13 wild type strain is known to control production of violacein in response to autoinducer
14 molecules such as C6HSL and C4-HSL (McClellan, Winson, Fish, Taylor, Chhabra et
15 al., 2007). The strain was routinely cultured aerobically in LB at 30 °C with or without
16 the addition of different concentrations of the bioactive phytochemicals. One mL of
17 overnight culture of the reported strain was centrifuged (19314 g, 10 min) (Eppendorf,
18 Hamburg, Germany) to precipitate the insoluble violacein. The culture supernatant was
19 discarded and 1 ml of DMSO was added to the pellet. The solution was centrifuged
20 (19314 g, 10 min) to remove the cells and then, the violacein was quantified at OD₅₈₅
21 using a UV-Vis spectrophotometer (Hewlett Packard 8453).

22

23 2.4. *Extraction and LC-MS/MS analysis of AHLs produced by E. carotovora and Y.* 24 *enterocolitica*

1 Fifty ml of LB and PDB, with or without the addition of bioactive
2 phytochemicals, were inoculated with an overnight culture of *Y. enterocolitica* and *E.*
3 *carotovora*, respectively for the extraction of AHLs. After 48 h incubation at 30 °C
4 bacterial cells were removed by centrifugation at 9632 g for 15 min at 4 °C and
5 supernatants were filtered through a Millex-GP 0.22 µm filter (Millipore Corp., USA).
6 Cell-free culture supernatants were extracted twice with acidified ethyl acetate (50 ml,
7 0.5% formic acid). After removal of the solvent under reduced pressure at 35 °C, the
8 residue was reconstituted in 2 mL methanol. This methanolic phase was concentrated in
9 a Speedvac® concentrator (Savant SPD 121P). Then, the residue was re-dissolved in
10 400 µL of methanol, filtered through a Millex-HV₁₃ 0.45µm filter (Millipore Corp.) and
11 stored at -20 °C until further analysis by LC-MS/MS. The percentage of
12 degradation/transformation of AHL produced by the interaction between each
13 phytochemical compound and the two AHLs was determined after mixed incubation of
14 the phytochemicals and a known concentration of AHLs in the selected culture broths.
15 To improve the detection and identification of AHLs, the extraction step with organic
16 solvents also led to concentrate the AHL present in the culture media, which are
17 produced in very low levels for bacterial cells.

18 The identification and quantification of the AHLs production by cultures in
19 stationary phase were studied by LC-MS/MS as previously described (Morin, Grasland,
20 Vallé-Réhel, & Haras, 2003; Truchado, Gil, Tomás-Barberán, & Allende 2009b). The
21 potential interference of the ingredients of the bacterial culture media was avoided by
22 means of an ethyl acetate extraction of the LB broth followed by the LC-MS/MS
23 analysis (Truchado et al., 2009b). The specific identification of each of the AHLs
24 extracted from the bacterial culture media was based on the detection of the fragment
25 ions of each AHL and the retention times of the standards.

1

2 2.5. *Determination of Growth Curves at the Selected Concentrations*

3 For bacterial growth assays, overnight cultures of the selected bacteria were
4 diluted (10^2 - 10^3 UCF/mL, corresponding to $OD_{600nm} = 0.08$) in buffered peptone water
5 (Scharlau Chemie, S.A.). Diluted cultures were grown in a sterile 96-well microtitre
6 plate (Nalge, Nunc International, Rochester, NY) with and without the addition of the
7 bioactive phytochemicals. The selected concentrations of the bioactive phytochemicals
8 were based on the QS inhibitory assay. The culture conditions were as previously
9 indicated with a final volume in each well of 200 μ L. A negative control containing 200
10 μ L of medium and bioactive phytochemicals was included. The addition of the selective
11 compounds to the culture media had no effect on the pH. The plates were incubated for
12 48 h at 30 °C with intermittent shaking and absorbance at 600 nm was measured every
13 hour using an Infinite® M200 micro plate reader (Tecan, Grödig, Austria). The
14 obtained values correspond to an average value acquired from eight replicate wells.
15 Bacterial growth curves were obtained in triplicate for each of the selected bioactive
16 phytochemicals. Experimental growth data for each bacterial strain were fitted to the
17 Baranyi function (Baranyi, Roberts & McClure, 1993) using a complementary tool for
18 Microsoft Excel (D-model, J. Baranyi, Institute of Food Research, Norwich, UK).
19 Kinetic parameters, including lag time and maximum specific rate (μ_{max}) for each
20 growth curve, were calculated from the generated Baranyi values. The coefficient of
21 determination (R^2) indicating the goodness-of-fit was also calculated.

22

23 2.6. *Statistical Analysis*

24 The differences in the growth, violacein inhibition and AHL production and/or
25 degradation of the selected bacteria with and without the addition of bioactive

1 phytochemicals were calculated using ANOVA and Brown-Forsythe tests, depending
2 on the homogeneity of the variances. When significant differences were observed,
3 Tukey's Multiple Range Test was applied using PASW Statistics 18 for Windows
4 (SPSS Inc., Chicago, IL, USA). A significance level of $P \leq 0.001$ was selected to
5 determine differences between samples. All experiments were performed in triplicate.

6

7 **3. Results and Discussion**

8

9 *3.1. Screening of bioactive phytochemicals with QSI activity*

10 The capacity of eleven bioactive phytochemicals compounds to inhibit AHL was
11 evaluated using the biosensor strain, *Chromobacterium violaceum*. To determine the
12 efficacy of each compound, a preliminary screening of three different concentrations
13 was carried out. The selection of the tested concentrations was based on available
14 literature (Huber et al., 2003; Choo *et al.*, 2009; Wang, Zhang, Wang, & Zhang, 2006;
15 Brackman et al., 2008, 2009; Singh et al., 2009). Compared to control, all the tested
16 bioactive phytochemicals significantly reduced production of violacein by *C. violaceum*
17 at the maximum tested concentrations, the most effective compounds being
18 cinnamaldehyde, ellagic acid, PE, resveratrol and rutin (Fig. 1 and Table 2). The
19 capacity of the different bioactive compounds to inhibit violacein production was, in
20 almost all the cases, concentration dependent (Fig. 1 and Table 2). Particularly notable
21 was that ellagic acid (at 4 $\mu\text{g/mL}$) and cinnamaldehyde, PE and resveratrol (at 50
22 $\mu\text{g/mL}$) inhibited violacein production by $85.86\% \pm 9.50$, $94.13\% \pm 1.77$, $76.72\% \pm$
23 6.85 and $97.98\% \pm 0.28$, respectively. A second screening was then carried out to
24 determine if reduced concentrations of PE and resveratrol were still effective in

1 inhibiting the violacein production. Table 3 shows that resveratrol (20 µg/mL) and PE
2 (20 µg/mL) inhibited the violacein production by 75.1 and 72.4 %, respectively.

3 According to our results, previous studies demonstrated the efficacy of plant
4 extracts, containing high concentrations of phenolic compounds, as QSI by measuring
5 the violacein pigment production by *C. violaceum* (Vattem et al., 2007; Choo et al.,
6 2006; Bodini et al., 2009; Brackman et al., 2009). Other authors have also demonstrated
7 that polyphenolic compounds, such as epigallocatechin gallate, catechin and curcumin
8 can interfere with bacterial QS (Vandeputte, Kiendrebeogo, Rajaonson, Diallo, Mol et
9 al., 2010; Lee, Churey, & Worobo, 2009; Rudrappa & Bais, 2008).

10 From all tested compounds, PE and resveratrol exhibited the highest inhibition
11 activities, similar to those shown by cinnamaldehyde, an inhibitor of the autoinducer-2
12 mediated QS (Brackman et al., 2008). It was observed that resveratrol was able to
13 inhibit completely the violacein production at any concentration tested. These results are
14 in line with Brackman et al. (2009) who detected an inhibition of violacein production
15 with a resveratrol concentration as low as 5.5 µg/mL. Pomegranate antimicrobial
16 activity has been previously described (Prashanth, Asha, & Amit, 2001); although, this
17 is the first time that the anti-QS activity of PE has been detected. This activity may be
18 due in part to the ellagic acid content of the pomegranate extract (1.4 µg /mL) but a
19 possible anti-QS activity of punicalagins can not be ruled out. Ellagic acid inhibited
20 violacein production by 86% when applied in concentrations as low as 4 µg/mL. This is
21 in disagreement with Huber et al. (2003), who did not detect QS inhibition activity in
22 concentrations up to 30-40 µg/mL of this compound. This difference in ellagic acid
23 effectiveness could be due to the different AHL biosensors used.

24 In this study, and after the screening of eleven phytochemical compounds, the
25 bioactive phytochemicals selected for further analyses were cinnamaldehyde at 50

1 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ (positive control), ellagic acid at $4 \mu\text{g/mL}$, PE at $20 \mu\text{g/mL}$, resveratrol at 20
2 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ and rutin at $200 \mu\text{g/mL}$.

3

4 3.2. *Inhibition of production and/or degradation-transformation of AHLs produced by*
5 *Y. enterocolitica and E. carotovora by selected bioactive phytochemicals*

6 The chemical analysis of AHLs in bacterial culture supernatants by LC-MS/MS
7 revealed that the major AHLs produced by *Y. enterocolitica* and *E. carotovora* were 3-
8 oxo-C6HSL and C6HSL (Fig. 2A and 3A), as previously described (Truchado et al.,
9 2009b; Ortori, Atkinson, Chhabra, Camara, Williams et al, 2007; Barnard & Salmond,
10 2007). The addition of selected phytochemical compounds (resveratrol, ellagic acid,
11 cinnamaldehyde acid, rutin and PE) to the culture media reduced AHL concentration
12 after 24 h incubation of both *Y. enterocolitica* (Fig. 2) and *E. carotovora* (Fig. 3) strains.
13 The observed reduction of AHL concentrations in the culture media corroborates the
14 QSI effect detected in the screening assay and indicates an inhibition of the QS system
15 of these two pathogenic bacteria. When the reduction of AHL concentration in culture
16 strain was determined taking as reference the AHL concentration of each bacterial
17 culture in LB broth without the addition of the selected phytochemicals, it was observed
18 that concentration of 3-oxo-C6HSL by *Y. enterocolitica* was considerably reduced with
19 the addition of cinnamaldehyde ($91.82 \pm 4.91\%$), PE ($88.43 \pm 1.51\%$), resveratrol
20 ($85.27 \pm 5.33\%$) and ellagic acid ($44.18 \pm 8.37\%$), whereas rutin showed no effect (Fig.
21 4). In general, C6HSL levels were less affected by phytochemical treatment.
22 Cinnamaldehyde and resveratrol were the most effective compounds reducing C6HSL
23 concentration by $61.47 \pm 11.94\%$, and $81.53 \pm 2.74\%$, respectively. Apparently, the
24 observed differences between the different susceptibilities of the tested AHLs to the
25 different phytochemical compounds have not been previously reported. This

1 observation could be relevant if both AHL play different functions; although nowadays
2 this is an unknown issue in these pathogenic bacteria. The concentration of AHLs
3 produced by *E. carotovora* was also reduced by the selected phytochemicals (Fig. 5).
4 When the concentration of 3-oxo-C6HSL was quantified by HPLC-MS/MS it was
5 observed that PE extract inhibited the AHL synthesis by more than 80%, while the rest
6 of the tested compounds reduced its synthesis by approximately 50%. Also different
7 susceptibilities between the inhibition of 3-oxo-C6HSL and C6HSL synthesized by *E.*
8 *carotovora* were observed. An inhibition of about 40-60 % of C6HSL synthesis was
9 observed when cinnamaldehyde, ellagic acid, PE and resveratrol were added, while
10 rutin only reduced AHL concentration by 10% (Fig. 5).

11 As previously mentioned, different research studies have demonstrated that
12 phytochemicals effectively interfere with AHL mediated QS, without inhibiting
13 bacterial growth (Vattem et al., 2007; Choo et al., 2006; Bodini et al., 2009; Brackman
14 et al. 2008, 2009; Vandeputte et al., 2010; Lee et al., 2009; Huber et al., 2003; Rudrappa
15 & Bais, 2008). However, as far as we know, unequivocal quantification of AHL
16 reduction by the selected phytochemicals in bacterial culture supernatants using LC-
17 MS/MS was not been carried out. Therefore, comparison among different studies
18 evaluating the efficacy of different bioactive compounds is not possible. Inhibition of
19 AHLs in cell media could be due to different phenomena including: 1) inhibition of
20 autoinducer synthesis and 2) the degradation-transformation of autoinducers, among
21 other possibilities well described in a previously published review by Ni et al. (2009). In
22 this study, we evaluated the percentage of degradation-transformation of autoinducers
23 by the phytochemical compounds, by quantifying the AHL concentration after mixed
24 incubation of the phytochemicals and a known concentration of AHLs in non-inoculated
25 culture broths. The obtained concentration was then compared to the quantification of

1 AHLs in an inoculated culture broth supplemented with the selected phytochemical
2 compounds to determine the inhibition of autoinducer synthesis. Fig. 4 and 5 show the
3 percentage of degradation-transformation observed in both pathogenic bacteria.
4 Degradation-transformation of 3-oxo-C6HSL and C6HSL was always lower than 20%
5 of the overall inhibition in both, *Y. enterocolitica* (Fig. 4) and *E. carotovora* (Fig. 5). In
6 general, C6HSL undergo more the degradation-transformation process in both strains
7 than 3-oxo-C6HSL. The degradation-transformation induced by ellagic acid (4 µg/mL)
8 considerably contributed to the total reduction of AHL concentration in the culture
9 broth (Fig. 4) whereas cinnamaldehyde did not produce any degradation-transformation
10 of the AHLs.

11

12 3.3. Growth curves of bacteria treated with selected concentrations of bioactive 13 phytochemicals

14 The effect of the previously selected concentrations of the most efficient bioactive
15 compounds on the growth curves of two different bacteria, *Y. enterocolitica* and *E.*
16 *carotovora*, was evaluated. The two strains were able to grow in culture media with the
17 selected bioactive phytochemicals and in general, no significant changes were observed
18 in maximum specific growth (μ_{max}) (Tables 2 and 3). It was also observed that the
19 maximum absorbance value attained in the stationary phase was the same when the
20 bacteria were grown in culture media supplemented with the different bioactive
21 phytochemicals (Tables 2 and 3). It could be concluded that the inhibitory effects of
22 selected bioactive compounds on AHLs production by *Y. enterocolitica* and *E.*
23 *carotovora* were demonstrated at selected concentrations which are lower than the
24 minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) of these bacteria. At the selected
25 concentrations of cinnamaldehyde (50 µg/mL), ellagic acid (4 µg/mL), PE (20 µg/mL),

1 resveratrol (20 µg/mL) and rutin (200 µg/mL) the growth rate was not affected but AHL
2 concentrations decreased. Thus, the decrease in AHL concentration could not be
3 attributed to any bactericidal or bacteriostatic effect on *Y. enterocolitica* and *E.*
4 *enterocolitica*.

5

6 **4. Conclusions**

7 The present study evidences the capacity of phytochemical compounds such as
8 cinnamaldehyde, ellagic acid, PE, resveratrol and rutin to interfere with the QS system
9 of *Y. enterocolitica* and *E. carotovora*. Our results showed that QS inhibition was due to
10 both the degradation-transformation of AHLs and the inhibition of AHL synthesis. In all
11 the cases, the selected concentrations were lower than the MIC of these bacteria because
12 no growth inhibition was observed. Thus, concentrations of cinnamaldehyde, ellagic
13 acid, PE, resveratrol and rutin below their MIC, might have antipathogenic activity
14 against *Y. enterocolitica* and *E. carotovora*, without imposing a selective pressure for
15 the development of resistance. Different studies have evaluated the capacity of different
16 phytochemical compounds to inhibit QS using biosensor strain. However, comparison
17 of results among different studies is difficult because different biosensor strains are used
18 and they are limited to the determination of a reduced range of AHL structures. On the
19 other hand, the use of chemical analysis and quantification of AHLs in bacterial culture
20 supernatants by LC-MS/MS could facilitate the evaluation of different strains and the
21 comparison among laboratories. Therefore, the use of standardized techniques to
22 evaluate the capacity of bioactive phytochemicals as QSI is desirable. Taking into
23 account the obtained results it is possible to think that natural extracts could be used as
24 anti-pathogenic natural agents, which could be applied in the development of novel non-
25 antibiotic drugs, for treating bacterial infections.

1

2 **Acknowledgments**

3 The research leading to these results has received funding from the European
4 Community's Seventh Framework Programme (FP7) under grant agreement no 244956
5 (project BEEDOC) and Consolider Ingenio 2010 project (CSD2007-00063 FUN-C-
6 FOOD) CICYT (project AGL2009-08603). M Larrosa is holder of a JAE-DOC contract
7 and P. Truchado is holder of a predoctoral scholarship from the Seneca Foundation.

8

9 **References**

- 10 Adonizio, A. L., Downum, K, Bennett, B. C., & Mathee, K. (2006). Anti-quorum
11 sensing activity of medicinal plants in southern Florida. *Journal of*
12 *Ethnopharmacology* 105, 427–435.
- 13 Al-Hussaini, R., & Mahasneh, A. M. (2009). Microbial growth and quorum sensing
14 antagonist activities of herbal plants extracts. *Molecules* 14, 3425–3435.
- 15 Atkinson, S., Chang, C., Sockett, R.E., Cámara, M. & Williams, P. (2006). Quorum
16 sensing in *Yersinia enterocolitica* controls swimming and swarming motility.
17 *Journal of Bacteriology* 188, 1451–1461.
- 18 Baranyi, J., Roberts, T. A., & McClure, P. (1993). A non-autonomous different equation
19 to model bacterial growth. *Food Microbiology* 10, 43–59.
- 20 Barnard, A. M., & Salmond, G. P. (2007). Quorum sensing in *Erwinia* species.
21 *Analytical and Bioanalytical Chemistry* 387, 415–423.
- 22 Bassler, B. L. (1999). How bacteria talk to each other: regulation of gene expression by
23 quorum sensing. *Current Opinion in Microbiology* 2, 582–587.

- 1 Bodini, S. F., Manfredini, S., Epp, M., Valentini, S., & Santori, F. (2009). Quorum
2 sensing inhibition activity of garlic extract and p-coumaric acid. *Letters in*
3 *Applied Microbiology* 49, 551–555.
- 4 Brackman, G., Defoirdt, T., Miyamoto, C., Bossier, P., Van Calenbergh, S., Nelis, H., &
5 Coenye, T. (2008). Cinnamaldehyde and cinnamaldehyde derivative reduce
6 virulence in *Vibrio* spp. by decreasing the DNA-binding activity of the quorum
7 sensing response regulator LuxR. *BMC Microbiology* 8, 1–14.
- 8 Brackman, G., Hillaert, U., Van Calenbergh, S., Nelis, H. J., & Coenye, T. (2009). Use
9 of quorum sensing inhibitors to interfere with biofilm formation and development
10 in *Burkholderia multivorans* and *Burkholderia cenocepacia*. *Research in*
11 *Microbiology* 160, 144–151.
- 12 Brahma, N. S., Singh, B. R., Singh, R. L., Prakash, D., Sarma, B. K., & Singh, H. B.
13 (2009). Antioxidant and anti-quorum sensing activities of green pod of *Acacia*
14 *nilotica* L. *Food and Chemical Toxicology* 47, 778–786.
- 15 Choo, J. H., Rukayadi, Y., & Hwang, J. K. (2006). Inhibition of bacterial quorum
16 sensing by vanilla extract. *Letters in Applied Microbiology* 42, 637–641.
- 17 Coates, A., Hu, Y., Bax, R., & Page, C. (2002). The future challenges facing the
18 development of a new antimicrobial drugs. *Nature Reviews Drug Discovery* 1,
19 895–910.
- 20 Cui, X. & Harling, R. (2005). N-Acyl-homoserine lactone-mediated quorum sensing
21 blockage, a novel strategy for attenuating pathogenicity of Gram-negative
22 bacterial plant pathogens. *European Journal of Plant Pathology* 111, 327–339.
- 23 Dong Y. H., Xu J. L., Li X. Z., & Zhang L. H. (2000). AiiA, an enzyme that inactivates
24 the acylhomoserine lactone quorum-sensing signal and attenuates the virulence of

1 Erwinia carotovora. Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the
2 United States of America 97, 3526–3531.

3 Fekete, A., Frommberger, M., Rothballer, M., Li, X., Englmann, M., Fekete, J.,
4 Hartmann, A., Eberl, L., & Schmitt-Kopplin, P. (2007). Identification of bacterial
5 N-acylhomoserine lactones (AHLs) with a combination of ultra-performance
6 liquid chromatography (UPLC), ultra-high-resolution mass spectrometry, and in-
7 situ biosensors. Analytical and Bioanalytical Chemistry 387, 455–467.

8 Fletcher, M. P., Diggle, S. P., Camara, M., & Williams, P. (2007). Biosensor based
9 assays for QS, HHQ and related 2-alkyl-4-quinolone quorum sensing signal
10 molecules. Nature Protocols 2, 1254–1262.

11 Gao, M., Teplitski, M., Robinson, J. B., & Bauer, W. D. (2003). Production of
12 substances by Medicago truncatula that affect bacterial quorum sensing.
13 Molecular Plant-Microbe Interactions 16, 827–834.

14 Huber, B., Eberl, L., Feucht, W., & Polster, J. (2003). Influence of Polyphenols on
15 Bacterial Biofilm Formation and Quorum-sensing. Zeitschrift für Naturforschung
16 C 58, 879–884.

17 Lee, H., Churey, J. J., & Worobo, R. W. (2009). Isolation and characterization of a
18 protective bacterial culture isolated from honey active against American
19 Foulbrood disease. FEMS Microbiology Letters 296, 39–44.

20 Lynch, S. V., & Wiener-Kronish, J. P. (2008). Novel strategies to combat bacterial
21 virulence. Current Opinion in Critical Care 14, 593–599.

22 Martin, C. A., Hoven, A. D., & Cook, A. M. (2008). Therapeutic frontiers: preventing
23 and treating infectious diseases by inhibiting bacterial quorum sensing. European
24 Journal of Clinical Microbiology 27, 635–642.

- 1 McClean, K. H., Winson, M. K., Fish, L., Taylor, A., Chhabra, S. R., Cámara, M.,
2 Daykin, M., Lamb, J. H., Swift, S., Bycroft, B. W., Steward, G. S. A. B., &
3 Williams, P. (1997). Quorum sensing and *Chromobacterium violaceum*:
4 exploitation of violacein production and inhibition for the detection of N-
5 acylhomoserine lactones. *Microbiology* 143, 3703–3711.
- 6 Morin, D., Grasland, B., Vallé-Réhel, C. D., & Haras, D. (2003). On-line high-
7 performance liquid chromatography-mass spectrometric detection and
8 quantification of N-acylhomoserine lactones, quorum sensing signal molecules, in
9 the presence of biological matrices. *Journal of Chromatography A* 1002, 79–92.
- 10 Ni, N., Li, M., Wang, J., & Wang, B. (2009). Inhibitors and antagonists of bacterial
11 quorum sensing. *Medicinal Research Reviews* 29, 65–124.
- 12 Ortori, C. A., Atkinson, S., Chhabra, S. R., Camara, M., Williams, P., & Barreto, D. A.
13 (2007). Comprehensive profiling of N-acylhomoserine lactones produced by
14 *Yersinia pseudotuberculosis* using liquid chromatography coupled to hybrid
15 quadrupole-linear ion trap mass spectrometry. *Analytical and Bioanalytical*
16 *Chemistry* 387, 497–511.
- 17 Prashanth, D., Asha, M. K., & Amit, A. (2001). Antibacterial activity of *Punica*
18 *granatum*. *Fitoterapia* 72, 171–173.
- 19 Rasmussen, T. B., & Givskov, M. (2006). Quorum sensing inhibitors: a bargain of
20 effects. *Microbiology* 152, 895–904.
- 21 Rudrappa, T., & Bais, H. P. (2008). Curcumin, a known phenolic from *Curcuma longa*,
22 attenuates the virulence of *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* PAO1 in whole plant and
23 animal pathogenicity models. *Journal of Agricultural and Food Chemistry* 56,
24 1955–1962.

- 1 Singh, B. N., Singh, B. R., Singh, R. L., Prakash, D., Dhakarey, R., Upadhyay, G., &
2 Singh, H. B. (2009). Oxidative DNA damage protective activity, antioxidant and
3 anti-quorum sensing potentials of *Moringa oleifera*. *Food Chemistry Toxicology*
4 47, 1109–1116.
- 5 Swift, S., Lynch, M. J., Fish, L., Kirke, D. F., Tomas, J. M., Stewart, G. S. A. B., &
6 Williams, P. (1999). Quorum sensing-dependent regulation and blockade of
7 exoprotease production in *Aeromonas hydrophila*. *Infection and Immunity* 67,
8 5192–5199.
- 9 Teplitski M., Robinson J. B., & Bauer W. D. (2000). Plants secrete substances that
10 mimic bacterial N-acyl homoserine lactone signal activities and affect population
11 density-dependent behaviors in associated bacteria. *Molecular Plant-Microbe*
12 *Interactions* 13, 637–648.
- 13 Truchado, P., López-Gálvez, F., Gil, M. I., Tomás-Barberán, F. A., & Allende, A.
14 (2009a). Quorum sensing inhibitory and antimicrobial activities of honeys and the
15 relationship with individual phenolics. *Food Chemistry* 115, 1337–1344.
- 16 Truchado, P., Gil, A., Tomás-Barberán, F., & Allende, A. (2009b). Inhibition by
17 chestnut honey of N-acyl-l-homoserine lactones and biofilm formation in *Erwinia*
18 *carotovora*, *Yersinia enterocolitica*, and *Aeromonas hydrophila*. *Journal of*
19 *Agricultural and Food Chemistry* 57, 11186-11193.
- 20 Vandeputte, O. M., Kiendrebeogo, M., Rajaonson, S., Diallo, B., Mol, A., El Jaziri, M.,
21 & Baucher, M. (2010). Identification of catechin as one of the flavonoids from
22 *Combretum albiflorum* bark extract that reduces the production of Quorum-
23 Sensing-controlled virulence factors in *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* PAO1. *Applied*
24 *and Environmental Microbiology* 76, 243–253.

- 1 Vattem, D. A., Mihalik, K., Crixell, S. H., & McLean, R. J. C. (2007). Dietary
2 phytochemicals as quorum sensing inhibitors. *Fitoterapia* 78, 302–310.
- 3 Vikram, A., Jesudhasan, P. R., Jayaprakasha, G. K., Pillai, B. S., & Patil, B. S. (2010).
4 Grapefruit bioactive limonoids modulate *E. coli* O157:H7 TTSS and biofilm.
5 *International Journal of Food Microbiology* 140, 109–116.
- 6 Wang, C., Zhang, H. B., Wang, L. H., & Zhang, L. H. (2006). Succinic semialdehyde
7 couples stress response to quorum sensing signal decay in *Agrobacterium*
8 *tumefaciens*. *Molecular Microbiology* 62, 45–56.
- 9 Xiong Y., & Liu Y. (2010). Biological control of microbial attachment: a promising
10 alternative for mitigating membrane biofouling. *Applied Microbiology and*
11 *Biotechnology* 86, 825–37.

12

1 **Figure Legends**

2

3 **Fig. 1.** Inhibition of violacein production by different bioactive compounds at 50 µg/mL
4 (A), 100 µg/mL (B) and 200 µg/mL (C). Vertical bars represent means of three
5 replicates ± standard deviation.

6

7 **Fig. 2.** MS/MS chromatograms of 3-oxo-C6HSL and C6HSL from supernatant of *Y.*
8 *enterocolitica* culture (A) and supernatants of *Y. enterocolitica* culture supplemented
9 with cinnamaldehyde (B) ellagic acid (C), PE (D), resveratrol (E) and rutin (F).

10

11 **Fig. 3.** MS/MS chromatograms of 3-oxo-C6HSL and C6HSL from supernatant of *E.*
12 *carotovora* culture (A) and supernatants of *E. carotovora* culture supplemented with
13 cinnamaldehyde (B) ellagic acid (C), PE (D), resveratrol (E) and rutin (F).

14

15 **Fig. 4.** Percentage of degradation-transformation and inhibition of synthesis of 3-oxo-
16 C6HSL (A) and C6HSL (B) in *Y. enterocolitica* cultures grown in LB broth
17 supplemented with different bioactive compounds. Vertical bars represent the standard
18 deviation (n = 8). Bars labelled with different letters (capital and small letters) indicate
19 significant difference at $P < 0.001$.

20

21 **Fig. 5.** Percentage of degradation-transformation and inhibition of synthesis of 3-oxo-
22 C6HSL (A) and C6HSL (B) in *E. carotovora* cultures grown in PDB broth
23 supplemented with different bioactive compounds. Vertical bars represent the standard
24 deviation (n = 8). Bars labelled with different letters (capital and small letters) indicate
25 significant difference at $P < 0.001$.

1 **Table 1.** List of phenolic phytochemicals.

2

Compound	Structure
Cinamaldehyde	
Chlorogenic acid	
Daidzein	
Dimethyl esculetin	
Ellagic acid	
Gallic acid	
Kinurenic acid	
Resveratrol	

Rutin

Vanillic acid

1
2

1 **Table 2.** Percentage of inhibition of violacein production of *C. violaceum* 494 by
2 different concentrations of ellagic acid. These data are representative of three
3 independent experiments. The results are the mean (n=9) \pm standard deviation. Values
4 labeled with different letters indicate significant difference at $P < 0.001$.

5
6
7

<i>Chromobacterium violaceum</i>	
Ellagic acid	% Inhibition
4 $\mu\text{g/mL}$	79.56 \pm 6.19a
8 $\mu\text{g/mL}$	93.91 \pm 1.95a
17 $\mu\text{g/mL}$	94.54 \pm 0.10a

8
9
10
11
12

1 **Table 3.** Percentage of inhibition of violacein production of *C. violaceum* 494 by
 2 different concentrations of pomegranate extract (PE) and resveratrol. These data are
 3 representative of three independent experiments. The results are the mean (n=9) ±
 4 standard deviation. Values labeled with different letters indicate significant difference at
 5 $P < 0.001$.

6

<i>Chromobacterium violaceum</i>		
Phenolic phytochemicals	Concentrations	% Inhibition
PE	10µg/mL	39.43 ±5.00b
	20µg/mL	72.40±6.00a
Resveratrol	10µg/mL	56.66±2.30a
	20µg/mL	75.13±1.20a

7

8

9

1 **Table 4.** Growth kinetic parameters of *Y. enterocolitica* grown in LB supplemented
 2 with different bioactive compounds.

3

Mean parameter value \pm SE ^a					
Compounds	Concentration	A	μ_{\max}	λ (h)	R ²
Control		1.39 \pm 0.02a	0.12 \pm 0.000d	9.68 \pm 0.06c	0.99
Cinamaldehyde	50 μ g/mL	1.34 \pm 0.07a	0.16 \pm 0.01a	12.45 \pm 0.22a	0.98
Ellagic acid	4 μ g/mL	1.39 \pm 0.07a	0.16 \pm 0.00a,b	11.89 \pm 0.20a	0.96
Pomegranate	20 μ g/mL	1.43 \pm 0.04a	0.15 \pm 0.00c	10.84 \pm 0.69b	0.98
Resveratrol	20 μ g/mL	1.42 \pm 0.04a	0.15 \pm 0.01b,c	10.22 \pm 0.15b,c	0.99
Rutin	200 μ g/mL	1.37 \pm 0.05a	0.12 \pm 0.00d	9.75 \pm 0.06c	0.99

4

5 ^a A, maximum absorbance value attained in the stationary phase; μ_{\max} , maximum
 6 specific growth rate (h^{-1}); λ delay time for microbial response; R², regression
 7 coefficient. The results are the mean (n = 3) \pm standard deviation. Values followed by
 8 different letters indicate significant difference at $P < 0.001$.

9

10

1 **Table 5.** Growth kinetic parameters of *E. caratovora* grown in PDB supplemented with
 2 different bioactive compounds.

3

Mean parameter value \pm SE ^a					
Compounds	Concentration	A	μ_{max}	λ (h)	R ²
Control		0.31 \pm 0.02a,b	0.03 \pm 0.00b,c	12.10 \pm 0.43b	0.99
Cinamaldehyde	50 μ g/mL	0.36 \pm 0.05a	0.04 \pm 0.00a	13.37 \pm 0.06a	1.00
Ellagic acid	4 μ g/mL	0.27 \pm 0.03a	0.02 \pm 0.00c,d	12.28 \pm 0.31a,b	0.97
Pomegranate	20 μ g/mL	0.25 \pm 0.08b	0.04 \pm 0.00a,b	13.19 \pm 0.12a,b	0.99
Resveratrol	20 μ g/mL	0.32 \pm 0.01a,b	0.04 \pm 0.00a,b	12.21 \pm 0.28b	0.97
Rutin	200 μ g/mL	0.28 \pm 0.01b	0.02 \pm 0.00d	12.59 \pm 0.08a,b	0.97

4

5 ^a A, maximum absorbance value attained in the stationary phase; μ_{max} , maximum
 6 specific growth rate (h⁻¹); λ dela time for microbial response; R², regression coefficient.

7 The results are the mean (n = 3) \pm standard deviation. Values followed by different
 8 letters indicate significant difference a $P < 0.001$.

9

10

1 **Figure 1.**

2

3

1 **Figure 2**

2

3

4

5

6

1 **Figure 3**

2

3

4

5

6

1 **Figure 4**

2

3
4

1 **Figure 5**

2

3